

TAXATION OF CRYPTOCURRENCIES AND NON FUNGIBLE TOKENS

Dr. P. SAI RANI

Head - Department of Finance
ICBM - School of Business Excellence,
Hyderabad, India
Email: sairani@icbm.ac.in;
Mobile: +91 98851 87681

VIJAYA KITTU MANDA

Doctoral Research Scholar,
GITAM Institute of Management,
GITAM Deemed to be University,
Visakhapatnam, A.P., India 530 045
Contact: +91 98495 19188;
Email: vijaykittu@hotmail.com
ORCID: 0000-0002-1680-8210

ABSTRACT

Virtual Digital Assets (VDA), such as Cryptocurrencies and Non Fungible Tokens (NFTs), have evolved as a new class of assets globally. With speculation and investing interest increasing around these products, governments worldwide are interested in taxing the profits or gains arising from the transactions. However, the taxation of virtual assets comes with several challenges, which this research article wishes to bring to the attention of the researcher community. Determination of tax jurisdiction, rate of taxation, onus, and level of disclosures required, taxing on gifts, and taxing on mining operations are some dimensions from the perspectives of different countries that this paper wishes to examine. Tax evasion will be inevitable if the Governments are not proactive and take a clear policy stand in the early stages of their growth. Learnings from this paper add to the body of knowledge on taxation and will be helpful to Investors, Regulators, and governments in formulating better tax policies.

Key words : Cryptocurrency, nft, taxation, tax compliance, tax jurisdiction, capital gains, digital assets

INTRODUCTION :

Blockchain-based financial engineering products such as cryptocurrencies and Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) have emerged as use-cases that can potentially revolutionize global economies in the way we trade and do business and commerce. Cryptocurrencies appear as digital or virtual currencies with the potential to replace fiat currency sooner or later. Stablecoins are a particular form of cryptocurrency close to this agenda (Richard and Didier 2018). Similarly, they promise to be a new form of investible asset class work (KuoChuen, Guo, and Wang 2017). These work in a decentralized manner and do not have any controlling authority from any country in the

world. Business transactions become more transparent, immediate, immutable, and secured by solid cryptographic encryption to serve the ledger of transactions like buy, sell, and transfer.

Cryptocurrencies are decentralized virtual currencies with no regulatory authority to watch or prove the transactions and thereby do not generally involve traditional financial intermediates such as banks. Cryptocurrencies allow trading and investment activities when used as an asset class. Adding to individual portfolios leads to significant and persistent risk-adjusted outperformance (Krückeberg and Scholz 2019). Thus, gains or profits can be derived, and the Governments and tax authorities are interested in taxing them.

Cryptocurrencies can be of two types – one meant to fund a specific project and the other designed for general or non-specific uses (García-Monleón, Danvila-del-Valle, and Lara 2021). The three functions that cryptocurrencies are expected to fulfill are- medium of exchange, a unit of account, and store of value by applying a designated methodical approach to examine each currency function separately (Levulytė and Đapkauskienė 2021).

Taxation on Cryptocurrencies

The early boom of Cryptocurrencies led to huge gains by traders and investors. However, the turbulence and increased volatility nature observed in late 2021 and early 2022 led to the fall in the gains by many speculators. Nevertheless, it fueled the interest of tax jurisdiction to tax the gains as and when they arise. Most Governments got caught in the dilemma of treating cryptocurrencies as a currency or as an asset class.

NEED OF THE STUDY

The need for this study arose because industry gap (real-life economic situation) for the following reasons:

1. Cryptocurrencies have emerged as a new asset class
2. Cryptocurrencies are difficult or almost impossible for any single Government to regulate
3. Cryptocurrencies gave healthy gains for traders and investors in 2020-21. Being a volatile asset class, it ferw the attention of investors and traders.

4. Governments across the globe need money by way of taxes in a post-COVID-19 pandemic era to fight inflation and other economic issues.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Research Type followed in this study is the Descriptive Approach. The Descriptive Approach aims to accurately and systematically describe a situation or phenomenon. This theoretical study examines the current situation, the emergence of cryptocurrency as a new asset class, and the need for taxation is the situation. The idea of this approach is to answer *what, where, when, and how* questions, but not the *why* part of the questions. Hence, this research focuses not on causation or its impact. Owing to the dynamics of the topic, data collection for this research work is from secondary data sources such as various Government websites, news, and media sources.

DISCUSSION

Regulation and taxation in various countries

Because Cryptocurrencies are sort of global, the question of tax jurisdiction is pivotal. The place from where the trading and investing in the asset happens plays a significant role. One of the first instances of an international level forum where the question of taxing transactions using cryptocurrencies was at the Declaration of the Brazilian Delegation during the Review of the OECD draft report on the fiscal challenges in the virtual economy in October 2017. Australia, Canada, and New Zealand did not comply with the 1922 Ordinance. Some Commonwealth countries have also chosen to design their tax systems. Instead of relying on the tax system of these countries, other countries have reformed

their tax system over time. They are significantly different from the 1922 Ordinance. In addition, many common law countries are off schedule.

The United States of America follows the dual legislative system in which both Federal and State Governments have the power and jurisdiction to frame regulations, such as those on Cryptocurrencies, to protect investors. Besides the SEC and IRS, several other regulators, such as the U.S. Commodity Futures Trading Commission (CFTC), Financial Crimes Enforcement Network (FinCEN), and the Financial Industry Regulatory Authority (FINRA), examined the various facets of cryptocurrencies (Sterley 2019). The U.S. markets even allowed crypto exchange companies to be listed. Coinbase's listing on the NASDAQ reflects the wide acceptance of cryptocurrencies.

The United Kingdom took a clear stand by saying that cryptocurrencies should be treated as capital assets. Exchanges dealing with them must register with the Financial Conduct Authority and take all precautions necessary to protect investors. Britain is a cryptocurrency integration leader. It is a supportive and convenient jurisdiction for driving cryptocurrency business. In addition, the state provides for start-ups linked to digital money. However, the Government is taking the ultimate stance on lawful regulation of digital money activities that have yet to be adopted. In substance, the cryptocurrency lies in the grey area (legislative vacuum).

Some tax jurisdictions employ a global system rather than a scheduling system such as Trade or Business Income and "all other income." Some jurisdictions with scheduling systems may not have a "sweep up" clause (Vincent 2021). Singapore, for example, does not tax capital gains.

Singapore is seen as allowing cryptocurrencies for transmission, exchange, or storage by taking an appropriate license. Singapore has some good legal provisions and guidelines for dealing with anti-money laundering and counter-terrorism financing.

El Salvador and the Central African Republic became the first two countries to declare Bitcoin as a legal currency/tender officially. Some countries took a more straightforward stand. China, for example, made a blanket ban on cryptocurrencies.

Cryptocurrency gains are taxed on capital gains and wealth taxes in Norway, Finland, and Germany. In Bulgaria, virtual currency is regarded as a financial instrument and imposed tax accordingly. In Austria, crypto is considered an intangible asset by the authorities. Several researchers are seen using anthropo-socio-cultural approaches to understand the linkages between taxation and the right to tax (Kateryna 2019).

In Romania, the income from cryptocurrencies is taxed only when an individual transfers the crypto into money or pays using crypto to others and must pay social contributions on earnings exceeding 601 lei. The taxpayer must submit the single taxation statement for the income from cryptocurrency under the legal deadline provided in the tax code, and total earnings are not taxed when the revenue is not exceeding the level of 600 lei. The law was introduced on the sale of cryptocurrencies by amending Tax Code (Zamfir, 2019) Law no. 30/2019, which approves and amends GEO No. 25/2018 and makes many changes in the Tax Code. The income from cryptocurrencies is treated under the "Revenue from other sources" (Lucian et al. 2020).

The European Parliament decided that the European Union go for cryptocurrency rules amid concerns that the digital tokens could be used to circumvent sanctions on Russia following the invasion of Ukraine. They sought to shorten the implementation time from the proposed two years from the E.U. law called Markets in Cryptoassets (MiCA) as a part of the digital finance strategy. First proposed in September 2020 (Jorge 2022), MiCA is believed to be an unprecedented regulatory approach aimed at transforming the European economy (Ferreira and Sandner 2021) and has four objectives as below :

1. Ensuring legal certainty for crypto-assets in scope
2. Supporting innovation and fair competition
3. Protecting customers, investors, and market integrity
4. To ensure financial stability with the inclusion of safeguards.

Cryptocurrencies are gaining more and more recognition as a part of trade and commerce and force many new regulations and tax affairs to consider by authorities. They are a subset of digital tokens commonly known as payment tokens and serve as a Payment method. However, the jurisdiction has not yet been granted fiat status. Tax authorities worldwide are interested in formulating frameworks and guiding the tax treatment of cryptocurrency transactions.

Cryptocurrency taxation in India

Cryptocurrencies in India are only taxed, but the regulation and legislation laws are still in progress. The central bank, the Reserve Bank of

India (RBI), is not keen on allowing cryptocurrency owing to potential injuries to the country's economic stability. Of course, the RBI has its plans to introduce a Central Bank Digital Currency – the Digital Rupee, and it is working towards that.

The Financial Bill of 2022 made the first official provisions for the taxation of gains from cryptocurrency (buying and selling) under Section 115BBH. The gifting of cryptos is taxed under Section 56(2)(x). It is described as property for a limited purpose only for this section so that that section can be useful and enforceable. Section 194S is put forward for 1 percent TDS on the transfer of cryptos. This tax program covered all the appearing virtual assets such as NFTs (non-fungible tokens), metaverse assets, digital currencies, and tokens.

The disallowance of expenditure and not allowing the offset of losses from the sale of one cryptocurrency with profits of another are seen as “detrimental steps.” Investors who invest in crypto have a substantial blow as taxation provisions such as setting off their losses and the acquisition cost of other assets such as gold, mutual funds, and stocks help investors lower tax incidence. These steps keep VDAs a class apart and not allowed to mingle with traditional investment products such as Equity shares or mutual funds. Clarifications were given that infrastructure costs incurred in mining cryptocurrencies or any virtual digital assets will not be allowed as a deduction under the Income Tax Act. Experts believe investors and players will move out of KYC-complaint systems to underground grey markets when the tax policies are not in their favor.

Crypto and other digital assets are highly risky and speculative, and platforms offering to buy and sell crypto can be risky for the investor without any regulation. The intention of the Union Government is clear - it views crypto trading as the same as other speculative activities such as gambling, lottery, or horse races. Because of this, the Centre is charging high taxes on crypto and other digital assets as

Investors always seek newer ways to pay lesser taxes on their profits. Indian investors would consider investing in U.S. ETFs that invest in cryptocurrencies to avoid high taxation. Indian investors had two options. The first is to prefer to pay a long-term (if held for more than 24 months for stock and 36 months for ETFs) capital gains of 20 percent with indexation benefits, plus applicable surcharge and fees. The second is to trade in the cryptocurrencies in India and pay a flat 30 percent and a one percent TDS when investing directly (Shrimi 2022b). Some investors were seen seriously considering the former route. Bitcoin Vest, a portfolio recently launched by Vested Finance, is an investment platform globally. For investors who do not want to buy any cryptocurrencies directly and give exposure in India. Bitcoin Vest is made with the equities of publicly traded companies exposed to Bitcoin.

The crypto market in India bounces back despite the 30 percent tax imposed on the profits from trading in cryptocurrency and as a digital asset of the country. Industry people are being positive toward this as many people were thinking and feared investing in crypto would be made illegal. WazirX (acquired and now owned by Binance) is one of the largest crypto exchange platforms. It reported a record 30 percent hike in sign-ups on its platform. Coinswitch, the nearest

competitor of WazirX, has reported a 35 percent daily hike in sign-ups from February 1, 2022, after the India announcement of the tax on cryptos. It became apparent that the clarity given on the taxation front has attracted trader and investor attention.

Though the Finance Bill formally stated the taxation aspects of cryptocurrencies for the first time, much confusion continued to exist. Tax authorities were busy giving clarifications and proposing amendments subsequently. Clearly, the tax treatment adopted by India for cryptocurrencies is similar to that of speculative activities such as lotteries and gambling. Overall, the tax policy is punitive and deterring (Lokeshwarri 2022).

GST on Crypto Exchanges

Recently, cryptocurrency and NFT exchanges in India witnessed increased activity. There are several reports that show that the Indian Government is considering a levy of GST at 28 percent on crypto activities. Ample discussion exists about the taxation of NFTs. It can be argued that NFTs are intangible and are made, marketed, and stored on physical servers. They can be bought, sold, transmitted, transferred, delivered, stored, and possessed. Also, the definition of goods includes intangible materials as well. Hence NFT may qualify as goods. Since the scope of supply under the GST law inter-alia includes a sale. Hence the sale of non-fungible tokens can be treated as a supply of goods. GST shall be leviable on such sale transactions (T.G. Team 2022).

WazirX, CoinDCX, and Zebpay have emerged as the leading platforms catering to this market. The Indian exchanges are seen moving their

crypto assets which were earlier traded in India, to jurisdictions outside India because they could come under the taxman's lens. Several instances such as this have triggered the crypto exchanges to fall under the scanner of the Tax Department, which began inspecting how crypto exchanges manage their cryptocurrency float and whether there is any part of the transaction where GST can be applied. Experts believe there could be a need for additional clarifications and rules before any action can be initiated. Inspection of the exchanges by the Tax Department was done on exchanges trying to run away from taxes (Amitoj 2022).

Tax compliances and checks

Cryptocurrency transactions may be reported by the banks and crypto exchanges to the tax authorities of their customer purchase and sell of virtual digital assets as the Government made the tax stand clear. Until now, the Tax Department had to rely on disclosures voluntarily on the transactions of Virtual Digital Assets. After implementing the law, the purchase and sale of digital assets will be recorded and shown under AIS (Annual Information Statement). AIS records at least 46 of the financial transactions done by the taxpayers in detail in a financial year.

The transactions related to Virtual Digital Asset have ensured the move that the availability of details with the authorities on a real-time basis and the change of revenue leakage would be lower and their going unexamined.

The taxation rules are once placed intentionally by the department for any way to the direction of reporting of digital asset transactions as an element of SFTs (specified financial transactions) appointed by prescribed entities (Shrimi 2022a).

Before implementing the new tax regime on crypto assets, several investors were seen booking their profits or transferring cryptocurrencies in their private wallets out of India before the new tax rules came into effect on April 1, 2022.

As many as a hundred entrepreneurs were reported to have moved out of India from the crypto ecosystem. Cryptoassets worth \$8 billion were anticipated to go out of India of \$80 billion of total crypto assets of the country (Rajesh 2022). Close neighbors like Singapore have a more transparent regulatory system and even charge lower taxes and hence were able to catch the attention.

Cryptocurrencies are facing similar challenges in several countries. Governments are making the roadmap to regulate private crypto trading. Some jurisdictions have already started doing this, though the journey will likely be longer. The Bank of England (BoE) is among the first to begin work on a regulatory plan. The BoE's Financial Policy Committee (FPC) felt that though the direct risks from cryptocurrencies to financial stability are limited, the immense growth happening around them would pose a threat in the future (Huw and David 2022).

NFTs and their Taxation

Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) are digital products that provide for the ownership of some unique properties or artwork made by you or someone else who wants to sell it digitally. The ownership will be given to the party willing to pay for ownership and get the right of artwork or properties, but the artwork will be available for free to use for all.

NFTs markets are busy with hefty money attached to music, art, tweets, and other digital collectibles.

The demand for tokens was seen increasing. Artist Beeple NFT was auctioned for \$69 million, while the animated flying pop-tart cat NFT was sold for U.S.\$600,000.

Bollywood actor Amitabh Bachchan has earned Rs.7.15 crores by selling NFTs, which include Madhushala - a collection of famous poems written by his father, posters, and images. The actor has paid up GST of Rs.1.09 crores and notice followed by the DGGI (Directorate General of Goods and Service Tax Intelligence) and the GST was attracted 18 percent IGST for the amount of Rs.7.15 crores. The actor has deposited the amount; tax authorities continue the investigations, and the authorities said Bachchan had an agreement with Singapore company Rhiti Entertainment Pte. Ltd. Bachchan is the first film celebrity (actor) to endorse NFTs (Nikunj 2022).

NFTs are on the radar of the IRS after knowing that digital tokens can bring the worth of fortunes and the taxable of such gains under most capital regimes. Tax evasion risk is potential in NFTs in the eyes of some tax authorities, including the IRS. The crypto world is showing its replication, said IRS Commissioner Charles Rettig at a Senate Finance hearing.

Tax Evasion

Indian Authority recovered Rs. 95.86 crores as CGST (Central Goods and Services Tax) with penalties and interest from eleven crypto exchanges and evaded around Rs.81.54 crores in GST. Out of the eleven crypto exchanges, the highest amount evaded of GST was from Zanmai Labs (WazirX) of Rs. 40.51 Crores. Platforms like Coin DCX, CoinSwitchKuber, and Goittus Technologies are reported to have evaded GST to a tune of Rs.15.70 crores, Rs.13.76 crores, and

Rs.3.85 crores. The Government was seen putting the crypto exchange platforms under the scanner (Shrimi 2022b).

Wazirx was charging commissions as trading fees, deposit fees, and withdrawal fees and making revenue from investors for buying and selling on their platform for cryptocurrency exchange and not paying tax to the Government. GST officials detected the evasion in January and served notice to WazirX. WazirX (Zanmai Labs) is a crypto exchange platform owned by Binance Investment Co, Seychelles.

Tax evasion is being investigated related to transactions of online gaming, e-commerce, and NFTs.

Deterrence Tax Treatment

As seen from the Indian taxation experience, the Government's intention appears to be deterrence tax treatment. However, past research has said that taxpayers will not well receive deterrence treatment and that tax evaders would proactively look for more methods to avoid taxes (Frey and Feld 2002). Even from an implementation point of view, past research improving tax service and government trust is more effective and relatively easier to implement than developing the taxpayers' positive behaviors (Dularif and Rustiarini 2021).

CONCLUSION

The tax structures related to cryptocurrencies from emerging economies are primarily towards deterrence rather than fostering the culture of cryptocurrencies. Being taxed at the highest tax bracket, disallowance of incidental expenditure, and not giving scope for offsetting losses on one cryptocurrency with profits of another are a few

salient features that do not motivate investors to try cryptocurrencies. Perhaps this was because the Governments wished to be first strict and harsh and test the waters before softening them out. Compliance in the form of TDS and GST was put on cryptocurrency exchanges making their life equally miserable by enforcing several compliance-related requirements. The overall delay in taking a policy stand hurts traders and investors who do not hesitate to change how they transact, including considering jurisdiction change.

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